

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14845985

09

A Comparison Study between Patella resurfacing Versus Non resurfacing with Patelloplasty in Total Knee Arthroplasty - A Case Series

Dr Richenkumar Shah Prof Dr Sudhir Kumar Rawat

Department of Orthopaedic
SBKS IMS&RC, Vadodara

ABSTRACT:

Introduction

Anterior knee pain following total knee arthroplasty (TKA) remains one of the important reasons for patient dissatisfaction. The management of patellofemoral joint is controversial and a decision whether to resurface the patella or not, is important. The present study compares the clinical and radiological outcomes between patellar resurfacing and nonresurfacing in patients undergoing bilateral TKA.

Aims

To Comparison Study Between Patella Resurfacing and Patelloplasty in Bilateral Total Knee Arthroplasty

Objectives

To Assess the: -

- Functional outcomes
- Complications If any after Patelloplasty or Patella Resurfacing
- Improvement in quality of life

Material and Method

- 40 patients were consecutively selected who to be operated for primary bilateral total knee replacement
- Patients had staged bilateral total knee replacement.
- All 40 patients were kept blinded. patella resurfaced on the side operated second.
- Prospective study removing the subjective bias by comparing the two techniques in a single patient operated for bilateral tkr and having patella resurfaced in one side and patelloplasty in other. Also all the surgeries were performed by a single surgeon surgeries and using the same implant removing the other biases and making the study more reliable and conclusions valid.

Observation and Results

- There were 11 males and 29 females.
- Youngest patient was 48 years age and eldest patient was 85. average age was 68.5. Average age in male was 65.09 and in female 62.61.
- Average b.m.i. was 24.9(19.1-27.5).
- Minimum follow up was 6 months and maximum follow up was 20 months.
- Operating time av. 15 minutes longer with 25cc more blood loss in resurfaced group.
- No acute infections.

Conclusion

There was no statistically significant difference in short-term clinical, functional, and radiological outcomes in the two groups and therefore, routine patellar resurfacing for patient undergoing TKA is not advantageous.

Key words: Patella Resurfacing, Patelloplasty, Total Knee Arthroplasty

INTRODUCTION

- Anterior knee pain following total knee arthroplasty (TKA) remains one of the important reasons for patient dissatisfaction. The management of patellofemoral joint is controversial and a decision whether to resurface the patella or not, is important. The present study compares the clinical and radiological outcomes between patellar resurfacing and non-resurfacing in patients undergoing bilateral TKA.
- At present there are three basic strategies for patella management during tkr:
 - 1)patellar resurfacing: reduced incidence of postoperative anterior knee pain,avoidance of secondary resurfacing, higher patient satisfaction, better overall func-tion, and low complication rate.
 - 2)non resurfacing: conservation of patellar bone, reduced likelihood of patellar osteonecrosis, more physiologic patellofemoral kinematics, ability to with-stand high patellofemoral forces, especially in younger and more active patients without the concern of prosthetic wear or failure, and ease of resurfacing in case of recalcitrant AKP.And it also avoids intraoperative and postoperative complications associated with patellar resurfacing⁵,
 - 3)Selective resurfacing attempts to identify those who are thought to have an improved clinical outcome with patellar resurfacing while avoiding potential complications associated with unnecessary resurfacing
- There has been constant debate between the treatment strategies which is still unresolved. Our study aimed to compare the two treatment stratagies in patella management paella resurfacing and modified patelloplasty specifically in Indian patients.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

- 40 patients were consecutively selected who to be operated for primary bilateral total knee replacement
- Patients had staged bilateral total knee replacement.
- All 40 patients were kept blinded. patella resurfaced on the side operated second.
- Prospective study removing the subjective bias by comparing the two techniques in a single patient operated for bilateral tkr and having patella resurfaced in one side and patelloplasty in other. Also, all the surgeries were performed by a single surgeon surgery and using the same implant removing the other biases and making the study more reliable and conclusions valid.

Indication:

osteoarthritis of knee severe enough to warrant total knee arthroplasty after an adequate trial of non-operative therapy.

Exclusion:

- A patellar realignment operation or any other major knee surgery such as high tibial osteotomy,
- previous patellectomy,
- patellar fracture,
- patellar instability,
- previous extensor mechanism procedures,
- previous unicondylar knee replacement,
- A history of septic arthritis or osteomyelitis

SURGICAL TECHNIQUE

Patella resurfacing

- Placement of a dome shaped 3 peg UHMWP component fixed with simplex bone cement using on lay technique.
- Patella component used are 26 mm, and 29 mm, 32 mm, 35 mm diameter with thickness of 5mm,6 mm ,7 mm and 8.5mm respectively.

Patelloplasty

- Patella osteophyte removed with smoothing of surface, partial rim cautery performed for partial neurectomy:only superficial electrocautery to a depth of no more than 1 mm in a circular fashion (360°) and within 5 mm of the edge of the patella.
- Subchondral decompression was done by using a 2.7mm drill bit to a depth of 2-2.5 cm.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

- There were 11 males and 29 females.
- Youngest patient was 48 years age and eldest patient was 85. average age was 68.5. Average age in male was 65.09 and in female 62.61.
- Average b.m.i. was 24.9(19.1-27.5).
- Minimum follow up was 6 months and maximum follow up was 20 months.
- Operating time av. 15 minutes longer with 25cc more blood loss in resurfaced group.
- No acute infections.
- The knee society scores, patellar scores and functional outcome results showed consistently improved results in both groups.

But there was no statistically significant difference between two groups at the final follow up.

	patelloplasty	Patella resurfacing
KSS	160.0	164.5
Patella score	23.69	23.75
Vas score	2.52	2.75

Incidence of anterior knee pain:

Anterior knee pain	patelloplasty	resurfacing
Gr 0	72.5%	75%
Gr 1	27.5%	22.55%
Gr 2	0%	2.5%
Gr 3	0%	0%

All the anterior knee pain patients were managed using non-surgical techniques which included use of analgesics, icepacks local ultrasonic. No patient required surgical

intervention. The pain was decreased in subsequent follow-ups.

The patient having grade -2 anterior knee pain in resurfacing group was having per operative patella fracture otherwise no significant difference found between two sides.

COMPLICATIONS

Patella #	01
Component loosening	00
Component #	00
Necrosis of patella	00
resurgeries	00

- Single patient (2.5%) having patella fracture on resurfacing side. The cause of which attributed to instrumentation error and osteoporosis.
- The patient had persistently higher vas score on the resurfaced side and patelloplasty side preference in activities.
- The patient was managed conservatively.
- There was consistent dissatisfaction for the outcome on the resurfaced side
- Other major patella-femoral complications i.e, loosening component, post operative patella fracture, patellar ligament rupture, necrosis of patella was not seen either of the groups possibly due to shorter follow up.
- Long term follows up results and outcome are yet to be seen.

X-RAY
Pre operative

Post operative

Left Patella resurfacing

Right Patelloplasty

Final follow up

CONCLUSION

- The results in both genders were comparable to overall results so can be said that resurfacing provides no extra benefits in either gender. Though average size of patella component used may be lower in female because small native patella.
- The knee society scores, patellar scores and functional outcome results showed consistently improved results in both groups. But the difference between the two groups was not significant. There was a single patient who got a fracture patella in a resurfacing group. So resurfacing is associated with whole new set of complications.
- The patella thickness in Asian population is less than the western population and required residual thickness of the bone must be set a level of 10-15 mm and final thickness of the component within 3 mm of native thickness. But minimizing the residual thickness of the bone can lead to increased risk of complications in longer follow up.
- So always resurfacing patella is not proved beneficial and it is advisable to reserve resurfacing to selected indications.

REFERENCES

1. Ranawat CS, Sculco TP: History and development of the total knee prosthesis at the Hospital of Special Surgery. In: Ranawat CS, ed. Total condylar knee arthroplasty, New York: Springer; 1985:3-6.
2. Levani J-P, McLeod HC, Freeman MAR: Why not resurface the patella? J Bone Joint Surg Br 1983; 65:448-451.
3. Scott RD, Turoff N, Ewald FC: Stress fracture of the patella following duopatellar total knee arthroplasty with patellar resurfacing. Clin Orthop Relat Res 1982; 170:147-151.
4. Waters TS, Bentley G: Patellar resurfacing in total knee arthroplasty. J Bone Joint Surg Am 2003; 85:212-217.
5. Bayley JC, Scott RD, Ewald FC, Holmes Jr GB: Metal-backed patellar component failure following total knee replacement. J Bone Joint Surg Am 1988; 70:668-674.
6. Dennis DA: Extensor mechanism problems in total knee arthroplasty. Instr Course Lect 1997; 46:171-180.
7. Dennis DA: Periprosthetic fractures following total knee arthroplasty. Instr Course Lect 2001; 8:379-389.
9. Keblish PA, Greenwald SA: Patella retention vs patella resurfacing in total knee arthroplasty. The patella: the unresolved problem in TKA. Presented at the 41st Annual Meeting of the American Academy of Orthopaedic Surgeons, Anaheim. Cal 1991.
10. Brick GW, Scott RD: The patellofemoral component of total knee arthroplasty. Clin Orthop Relat Res 1988; 231:163-178.
11. Levitsky KA, Harris WJ, McManus J, Scott RD: Total knee arthroplasty without patellar resurfacing. Clin Orthop Relat Res 1993; 286:116-121.
12. Pettine KA, Bryan RS: A previously unreported cause of pain after total knee arthroplasty. J Arthroplasty 1986; 1:29-33.
13. Scott RD: Total knee arthroplasty. Philadelphia, Saunders, 2006.
14. Soudry M, Mestriner LA, Binazzi R, Insall JN: Total knee arthroplasty without patellar resurfacing. Clin Orthop Relat Res 1986; 205:166-170.

Conflict of Interest: Nil

Acknowledgement: Nil

Funding: Nil